

DAMAGE MECHANISMS IN HEMP-FIBRE WOVEN FABRIC COMPOSITES STUDIED BY ACOUSTIC EMISSION

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SUMMARY

This study deals with hemp-fibre woven fabric/epoxy composites. A multi-scale analysis is developed to characterise damage mechanisms in woven fabric composites by using acoustic emission. Event amplitude has been studied on single hemp yarn, neat epoxy resin and composite to identify damage mechanisms in woven fabric composites.

Keywords: Acoustic emission, Natural fibre composites, Multi-scale analysis, Woven fabric composites, Damage mechanisms.

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials are extensively used in different industry fields such as aeronautics, offshore and automobile. It is thus necessary to understand their damage mechanisms to achieve composite structure design and predict their lifetime.

This study deals with hemp-fibre woven fabric/epoxy composites. A considerable interest has recently appeared in natural fibre composites owing to the difficulty encountered in synthetic fibre recycling. Different studies have shown that these materials could reduce environmental impact [1]. Many authors have already studied flax fibre composites [2-3] or short-hemp-fibre reinforced composites [4-6]. And, more recently, some studies concern long hemp yarn reinforced unidirectional composites [7]. In the present study, hemp yarn fabrics were used as reinforcement.

Acoustic emission (AE) technique is well known as a powerful method to analyse damage mechanisms in composites. This technique has been widely used on carbon or glass/polyester composites [8-9], carbon or glass/epoxy composites [10-13] or polymer reinforced composites [14]. However, few studies based on acoustic emission have been already published for natural fibre composites [15].

Several types of damage occur in composites subjected to mechanical loading such as matrix cracking, delamination and fibre debonding, and lead to the material failure. Each damage mechanism generates a specific AE signal. Thence, many authors have developed various AE experimental programs adapted to different materials. For cross-ply laminates, tensile tests on neat resin and [0], [45] and [90] unidirectional composites can be performed to characterise damage [9,14]. Then, the dominant mode of damage developed in each orientation is associated to the corresponding AE event amplitude. For example, Huguet et al. [9] have studied unidirectional glass fibre reinforced

polyester composites and identified matrix cracking thanks to tensile tests on neat resin, and fibre debonding from tests on [45] and [90] off-axis laminates.

Damage mechanisms in woven fabric composites are much more complicated than in UD laminates because of the complex meso-structure of woven fabric composites [16-17]. Therefore, many authors have developed additional tests or experimental methods to study these composites [10,12,18]. For example, Scida et al. [10] have realised bending and shear loading tests to study twill-weave and satin-weave glass/epoxy composites. Lomov et al. [12] have combined acoustic emission and X-ray inspection to identify damage mechanisms in woven fabric carbon/epoxy composites.

The purpose of this study is to characterise damage mechanisms in hemp-fibre woven fabric composites using acoustic emission. A multi-scale analysis of the AE event amplitude distributions has been performed. Tensile tests have been realised on single hemp yarn and on neat epoxy resin to determine specific acoustic emission range for each material. The AE analysis coupled with microstructural observations enables to identify damage mechanisms in hemp/epoxy composites.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Studied Materials

Composites used in this study were made of hemp-fibre woven fabrics and EPOLAM 2022 epoxy resin, with fibre volume fractions from 0.35 to 0.4. The stacking sequence is [0/90]₇. Composite plates have been manufactured by VALAGRO (Poitiers-France), by using resin injection moulding technique. Woven fabric composites and neat epoxy resin were processed with identical optimised heating procedure (24h at room temperature, 4h at 50°C, 2h at 80°C and 4h at 100°C) [19]. After these processing conditions, the glass transition temperature of the epoxy resin is about 85°C. The microstructure is based on four different scales (Fig. 1):

- the hemp primary fibre from plant stem,
- the hemp yarn, made of several hemp fibres twisted with a mean angle of 11°,
- the ply, made of 4/4 hemp taffeta-weave fabric and epoxy resin,
- the hemp-fibre woven fabric/epoxy composite [0/90]₇.

Fig. 1. Different scales in the microstructure of hemp-fibre woven fabric/epoxy composite.

Hemp yarn tensile test

Single yarn tensile tests were performed on an Instron E1000 electropuls testing machine with a load cell of 250N and a crosshead speed of 0.5mm/min. Specimen gauge length was about 25 mm. To ensure that the yarn was sufficiently clamped during

tensile test, two thin glass/epoxy composite end-tabs have been added (Fig. 2). Before testing, the cross-section area was calculated from the mean diameter by assuming that yarn cross-section is circular. For each sample, it was determined by five optical measurements along the gauge length with a Leica Microsystems optical microscope and the IM 50 software program.

Resin and composite tensile tests

Composites and neat resin specimens (Fig. 2) were loaded in uniaxial tension on an Instron 4505 testing machine with a crosshead speed of 0.5mm/min. Strain was measured by an extensometer centered on one side of the tested specimen. Fracture surfaces were analysed with a Jeol 6400 scanning electron microscope (SEM).

Acoustic emission

For each material, during tensile tests, AE events have been recorded with a PCI-2 acoustic emission system (Physical Acoustics Corporation). AE signals were detected through wide band sensors with a resonant frequency at 300 kHz and an active surface diameter of 10 mm. For each test, the sensor output was amplified by 40 dB and a bandwidth of 1kHz-3MHz was used. The threshold level was set up as 50dB for composites and single hemp yarn and 25dB for matrix, and the system timing parameters were: 200 μ s for the peak definition time to enable the determination of the AE waveform maximum, 800 μ s for the hit definition time to enable the system to determine the end of the hit, 1000 μ s for the hit lockout time to inhibit the measurement of reflections and late-arriving parts of the AE signals.

A specific grease was used to ensure the contact between sensors and specimen surface. The sensors were fixed thanks to clips directly on resin and composite specimen surfaces and on the glass/epoxy composite end-tabs for hemp yarn tensile tests (Fig. 2). Before tensile testing, the data acquisition system was calibrated for each kind of sample, according to pencil lead breaks. The wave velocity was deduced from the distance between the two sensors and used in the software to localize the events. Thus, only the events located between the two sensors (hatched area in Figure 2) were recorded. Then, for each test, the AE count number has been plotted versus the event amplitude. It allowed to check that ambient noises have been correctly suppressed thanks to the applied parameters (Fig. 3).

Fig. 2. Specimen geometry with AE sensors for: (a) hemp/epoxy composite, (b) neat epoxy resin, (c) single hemp yarn.

Fig. 3. Example of an AE curve, counts (in log scale) versus event amplitude for hemp-fibre woven fabric composites [0/90]₇

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Multi-scale analysis

A multi-scale analysis of AE event amplitude was developed. At first, the acoustic signature of each material: neat resin, hemp yarn and hemp/epoxy composite [0/90]₇ has been characterised. Tensile tests with AE recording have been performed on sets of four to ten specimens according to the result reproducibility for each material [20]. Then, the data were added and averaged to create an experimental curve of the AE event amplitude distribution for each material. A statistical Laplace-Gauss model was used to fit the AE experimental curves. Two parameters of the Laplace-Gauss model were studied: the mode, which represents the population mean, and the range, which is the full width at half maximum (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Characteristic parameters in Laplace-Gauss model [21].

Moreover, in order to represent the average number of AE events recorded during tensile tests, the Y maximum value was taken equal to the average number of AE events recorded in the « A-domain » (Fig. 4) and noted n_{Aav} .

Fig. 5. Experimental and statistical curves of the AE event amplitude distributions in :
a) hemp yarn b) neat resin c) hemp/epoxy composites [0/90]₇.

Figure 5 shows the experimental curve of the AE event amplitude distributions and the corresponding statistical model for each material: hemp yarn (Fig. 5a), neat resin (Fig. 5b) and hemp/epoxy composites (Fig. 5c).

Figure 5a shows that, for hemp yarn, the AE event amplitude distribution is well fitted with a Laplace-Gauss model. The mode for AE event amplitude distribution of hemp yarn is 65 dB and the range is between 52 dB and 78 dB. The average number of events recorded for each hemp yarn specimen, $n_{Aav \text{ yarn}}$, is 93 and can be associated with damage such as fibre fractures.

For the epoxy resin, the average number of events recorded for each specimen, $n_{Aav \text{ resin}}$, is relatively low (about 5.4). The mode, determined from the Laplace-Gauss fitting, is 49 dB and the range is between 32 and 65 dB. These parameters characterise major damage mechanisms in resin i.e. initiation and propagation of cracks.

The experimental AE amplitude curve obtained for hemp/epoxy woven fabric composites is shown in Figure 5c. The average number of events, $n_{Aav \text{ composite}}$, is 325. This number is larger than those obtained for neat resin and for hemp yarn; it reveals the occurrence of numerous damage in these composites. Three different Laplace-Gauss laws were necessary to fit the experimental AE amplitude distribution of the composite. Results in Figure 5c show three different modes located at 53 dB, 59 dB and 68 dB with their corresponding ranges: 50 and 57 dB, 54 and 64 dB and 64 and 72 dB respectively.

Identification

As previously mentioned, the experimental curve of AE amplitude in hemp/epoxy composite shows three peaks. The Figure 6 exhibits the comparison between the experimental and statistical curves for the composite and the statistical laws relative to

the neat resin and the single hemp yarn. The first peak recorded in the composite corresponds to the mode of the neat resin (53 vs. 49 dB) and the third peak is very close to the hemp yarn one (68 vs. 65 dB). These results reveal that AE amplitude signatures of resin and hemp yarn have been found in composite AE amplitude signal; the first peak of the composite can be associated to matrix damage and the third one corresponds to reinforcement damage. It demonstrates the validity of the multi-scale characterisation method developed in this study. However, the second peak relative to the composite, located in the amplitude range [54 dB, 64 dB] with a mode at 59 dB is not clearly identified. It can also be noticed that the AE event number recorded for the matrix is larger in composite than in neat resin (200 vs. 5.4). This difference can be due to the presence of reinforcements, which increases the damage initiation zones in the matrix.

Fig. 6. AE event amplitude distributions: experimental and statistical curves of hemp/epoxy composites $[0/90]_7$, and statistical curves of single hemp yarn and neat resin.

Composite fracture surfaces have been observed by using SEM technique as illustrated in Figure 7. Three types of damage can be seen:

- in reinforcement: partial fibre fracture in yarn and yarn fracture (Fig. 7.1a and Fig. 7.1b) ;
- in matrix: matrix cracking and matrix fracture area (Fig. 7.2a and Fig. 7.2b) ;
- at the fibre/matrix interface: partial or complete yarn debonding (Fig 7.3a, 7.3b and Fig. 7.3c).

It can be noticed that no delamination has been observed; it can be explained by the woven fabric composite architecture.

Fig. 7. SEM observations of fracture surfaces in hemp fibre woven fabric composites : damage in hemp yarn reinforcement (1), in matrix (2) , and at fibre/matrix interface (3).

Results show that the two first types of damage can be clearly linked to the two peaks observed in the AE curve of the composite, corresponding to the modes of neat resin and single hemp yarn. Thus, from the microscopic observations, the second AE peak of the composite, which is located between those of matrix and reinforcement, can be attributed to interfacial damage mechanisms (Fig. 6). Thanks to the multi-scale analysis of AE amplitude signature of composite elementary components, damage mechanisms in woven fabric composites have been characterised. The different modes and ranges identified and their corresponding damage mechanisms are summarised in Table 1.

Table. 1. Mode and range of AE amplitude distribution for each material and associated damage mechanisms.

Material	Mode (dB)	Range (dB)	Dominant damage mechanism
Hemp yarn	65	52-78	Fibre damage and fracture
Neat resin	49	32-65	Polymer cracks
Hemp /Epoxy composites [0/90] ₇	53	50-57	Matrix cracks
	59	54-64	Interface Fracture Debonding
	68	64-72	Reinforcement damage and fracture

Damage mechanisms tracking in hemp/epoxy composites.

AE events have been recorded throughout the hemp/epoxy composite tensile tests. Figure 8a shows an example of stress-strain curve with the corresponding AE event cumulative number for a hemp/epoxy composite specimen. We can see in Figure 8a that until 13% of the ultimate strain, acoustic activity is low. The threshold of the curve of

the AE event cumulative number is about 14% of the ultimate strain and can be associated to material damage initiation. Then, there is an increase of AE event number, which can be linked to material damage developments. At the end of the test, from 69% of the ultimate strain, AE activity grows significantly while damage increases up to specimen failure.

Additional information can be obtained thanks to multi-scale analysis: each type of composite damage mechanism can be followed during tensile tests. Figure 8b shows an example obtained for hemp-fibre/epoxy composite: AE events amplitude versus normalised strain. The AE events have been characterised by using different symbols according to the amplitude ranges previously identified (Tab. 1). Therefore, it enables to distinguish three types of damage phenomena occurring in reinforcement, matrix or interface. This allows the partition of the AE events amplitude versus normalised strain curve (Fig. 8b) into three distinct areas. From 0 to 42 % of the ultimate strain (1st area in Figure 8b), only events linked to matrix and interface damage have been detected. These events can be associated with the initiation and growth of matrix cracks and with fibre/matrix interface debonding. AE phenomena linked to interface and reinforcement have been recorded in the second area, from 42% to 70% of the ultimate strain, and correspond to the fibre/matrix interface degradation coupled with reinforcement damage. At the end of the test (third area in Figure 8b), lots of AE events have been recorded; there is simultaneously, a large number of events linked to interfacial phenomena and few events for reinforcement and matrix damage. This simultaneous increase in the three types of damage previously identified explains the increase in cumulative AE event number illustrated in Figure 8a which leads to the composite failure.

Fig. 8. Example for hemp woven fabric composite $[0/90]_7$: (a) stress-strain curve with the cumulative AE event number, (b) AE event amplitude versus normalised strain.

Results obtained thanks to multi-scale analysis of AE event distributions have enabled to identify and follow the development of damage mechanisms in hemp/epoxy composites. This combined analysis has great potential to investigate the behaviour of these composites.

Energetic evaluation

In this study, AE amplitude analysis is carried out to investigate damage mechanisms of composite. Various parameters are recorded with acoustic emission, such as amplitude, frequency, energy data or waveform parameters. Some studies have used a multivariable data analysis to characterise the development of damage [9,13,22]. Many of them have shown a clear correlation between acoustic emission amplitude and damage mechanisms in composite [11,23]. However, damage mechanisms are energetic data. Thus, it is necessary to compare amplitude and energetic data. Figure 9 shows, for each hemp/epoxy composite, the energy of each AE event versus AE amplitude. Amplitude ranges previously identified for matrix and reinforcement (Tab. 1) are also plotted in Figure 9. It can be seen that the amplitude ranges of matrix and reinforcement correspond to distinct energetic levels. It demonstrates that damage phenomena with specific energy levels can also be discriminated by different amplitude ranges. Moreover, Figure 9 shows that the interfacial phenomena located in the middle amplitude range with a mode at 59 dB also correspond to a middle energetic level. These results validate the analysis of AE amplitude distributions to characterise damage mechanisms in hemp-fibre woven fabrics/epoxy composites.

Fig. 9. Example of an AE energy-amplitude (log scale) curve for a hemp-fibre woven fabric composite $[0/90]_7$

CONCLUSION

Damage mechanisms in hemp-fibre woven fabric composites have been identified by using acoustic emission technique. A multi-scale analysis has been developed to characterise AE amplitude signatures of the elementary components of the composite. Tensile tests have been performed on single hemp yarn and neat epoxy resin, and a statistical analysis of AE amplitude signals has been realised. AE analysis has been correlated with microscopic observations. This study has enabled to identify three types of damage in hemp/epoxy composites: matrix cracking, interfacial debonding and reinforcement degradation. Work is in progress to associate these AE results with a mechanical damage model.

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